

A Clinical Comparative Evaluation of Bupivacaine and Ropivacaine for Epidural Anaesthesia in Adult Patients Undergoing Lower Extremity Surgery

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Abstract:

Background: Post-operative pain may produce deleterious effects on respiratory, cardiovascular, neuroendocrine and gastrointestinal systems of our body. Epidural anaesthesia reduces the incidence of many major post-operative complications. The advantage of epidural anesthesia is the ability to maintain continuous anaesthesia after placement of an epidural catheter which can be extended into post-operative period for analgesia using lower concentration of local anaesthetic drugs alone or in combination with different adjuvants.

Materials and Methods: 100 cases undergoing elective lower extremity surgery between ages 18-60 years of both sexes with ASA grade I were selected randomly and divided into two groups of 50 cases each. All patients received Tab Diazepam 10mg orally the night before surgery. Inj. Ondansetron 4 mg iv and Inj. Ranitidine 50 mg (slow iv drip) were given half an hour before operation. One group received 20 ml of 0.75% ropivacaine hydrochloride (Group A) and other group received 20 ml of 0.5% bupivacaine hydrochloride (Group B). Onset, duration, peak height and time taken for the sensory block to regress by 2 dermatomes was recorded. Onset, duration and degree of motor block, hemodynamic parameters and side effects were recorded. Quality of post-operative analgesia was recorded. Students t test (Unpaired t test), Chi square test or Fishers exact test were used for statistical analysis.

Results: The onset and duration of sensory block, hemodynamic effects after administration of the drugs, the quality of post-operative analgesia produced and the incidence of side effects like hypotension, bradycardia, nausea, vomiting, pruritus and shivering produced by 0.5% bupivacaine and 0.75% ropivacaine are similar. The onset of motor block is similar for both the drugs, but the duration of motor block is considerably longer with bupivacaine. Bupivacaine produces a greater degree of motor block.

Conclusion: Bupivacaine (0.5%) and ropivacaine (0.75%) produce similar epidural anaesthesia with the only exception that the degree and duration of motor block is less with ropivacaine.

Keywords: Epidural Anaesthesia, Bupivacaine, Ropivacaine, Lower Extremities Surgery.

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Introduction

Pain is one of the bitterest experience in the lives of mankind. Surgical pain is an acute pain and is defined as conscious perception of a noxious

stimuli. Although pain has teleological function in warning about injury, post-operative pain may produce deleterious effects on respiratory, cardiovas-

cular, neuroendocrine and gastrointestinal systems of our body.[1] Orthopaedic procedures of the lower limb are well suited for epidural block technique. Epidural anaesthesia reduces the incidence of many major post-operative complications like deep vein thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary embolism (PE), blood loss and respiratory complications. The advantage of epidural anaesthesia is the ability to maintain continuous anaesthesia after placement of an epidural catheter, thus making it suitable for procedures of long duration. This feature also enables the use of this technique into the post-operative period for analgesia using lower concentration of local anaesthetic drugs alone or in combination with different adjuvants. In the past lignocaine was used and now bupivacaine is used extensively to provide adequate anaesthesia and analgesia in patients undergoing surgeries in lower extremity. Ropivacaine is a new local anesthetic with similar analgesic property and little lesser motor blocking property as bupivacaine but with less propensity of cardiotoxicity. Kallio H et al concluded that the major advantage with ropivacaine is a faster motor recovery compared to bupivacaine. Chan Jong Chung et al found that Ropivacaine produced similar and clinically effective spinal anesthesia with shorter duration of sensory and motor block, compared to hyperbaric bupivacaine in caesarean patients. [2]

This study was designed and conducted to compare onset and duration of sensory and motor block, degree of motor block, effects on hemodynamic status and post-operative analgesia of epidurally administered bupivacaine and epidurally administered ropivacaine in patients undergoing lower extremity surgery and also to compare the side effects profile of both the drugs. [3]

Materials and Method

This Prospective, randomized, double blinded comparative study was conducted in the Orthopaedics operation theatre under the Department of Anaesthesiology of Diphu Medical College & Hospital, Diphu from July, 2022 to June, 2023 after approval from the Institutional Ethical committee.

100 cases undergoing elective lower extremity surgery between ages 18-60 years of both sexes with ASA grade I were included. Patients who did not give consent, had allergy to any local anaesthetic, ASA category more than 2, had Infection over site of needle insertion, had vertebral anomalies, on anti-platelet treatment or with bleeding diseases or coagulopathies or had preexisting neurological, hepatic, cardiac, renal, endocrine, metabolic or psychiatric disorders were excluded.

The study was done between two groups that is group A (ropivacaine) and B (bupivacaine). The first patient was allocated one of the study drugs

randomly, then each subsequent patient was alternately allocated to ropivacaine or bupivacaine group till desired sample achieved. A detailed pre anaesthetic checkup was done prior to day of surgery and preoperative fasting was ensured before operation according to guidelines. The patients were explained in detail about the procedure of lumbar epidural block and written informed consent was taken. Skin sensitivity test for both drugs was done in pre anaesthetic checkup. Only patients fit for pre anaesthetic checkup were taken for surgery under study and Tab Diazepam 10mg was given orally the night before surgery.

Inj. Ondansetron 4 mg iv and Inj. Ranitidine 50 mg (slow iv drip) were given half an hour before operation. Standard monitoring was carried out in the form of heart rate, arterial pressure and SpO₂. Continuous ECG monitoring was done. All patients were preloaded with 15 ml/kg of Ringer's Lactate solution over 15 minutes before administering epidural block.

Under all aseptic and antiseptic precautions, epidural anaesthesia was given in sitting position using 18 G Tuohy needle at L2-3 or L3-4 interspace. Epidural space was identified by loss of resistance to air technique. An epidural catheter was introduced into the epidural space and it was secured by sterile gauge and adhesive plaster over patients back. A test dose of 3ml of the local anaesthetic was injected and vitals observed for 3 minutes to rule out intravascular or intrathecal injection. After ensuring proper placement of the epidural catheter, the study drug was slowly injected in small increments with repeated aspiration test over 5 minutes. Monitoring of the vital signs was continued throughout the procedure. Then the patients were made supine. The patients were administered oxygen at the rate of 4 L/min through face mask throughout the procedure. No other analgesic was given to the patients intraoperatively. The surgery was allowed after the block reached T-10 level. The level of sedation was assessed intraoperatively using four-point sedation scale.

The following parameters were noted:

Onset of sensory block (Assessed by pin prick method and loss of sensation to cold every 3 minutes at T10 and S3 defined as the time in min from local anaesthetic solution injection to loss of pain sensation to pin prick at the level)

Duration of sensory block (Assessed every 15 minutes by pin prick method at T10 and S3 defined as from onset of sensory block to regression of sensory block to the level.)

Time taken for the sensory block to regress by 2 dermatomes was also noted. Maximum intraoperative VAS score was noted.

Onset of motor block: Assessed every 3 minutes by Bromage scale (Bromage grade 1 and Bromage grade 2 used).

Duration of Motor Block: Assessed every 15 minutes. Duration of Bromage grade 1 motor block was assessed from the onset of motor block to regaining of motor power at hip joint. Duration of Bromage grade 2 motor block was assessed from the onset of motor block to regaining of motor power knee joint.

Degree of motor block: The maximum degree of motor block attained (Bromage score) was noted

Peak Height of Sensory Block: The highest dermatomal level blocked was noted.

Hemodynamic parameters: Heart rate, mean arterial pressure and SpO₂ were noted at 0 (preblock) 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180 minutes from administration of epidural anaesthesia.

Side effects – nausea, vomiting, bradycardia, hypotension, pruritus and urinary retention were noted if they occurred and managed accordingly.

Post-operative analgesia: After the operation when the patients complained of pain (VAS score >3) a top up was given using either 8ml of 0.125% bupivacaine hydrochloride (by diluting 2ml of 0.5% to 8 ml) or by using 8ml of 0.2% ropivacaine hydrochloride. Onset of post-operative analgesia was taken as the time from injection of top up dose to the time the patient first got relieved of pain. This was assessed by Visual Analogue Scale.

For statistical analysis, raw data was entered into MS-Excel spreadsheet and analysed by Data Analysis Toolpack available in MS-Excel 2007.

Numerical parameters were compared between groups by Students t test (Unpaired t test). Categorical variables were compared between groups by Chi square test or Fishers exact test as appropriate. All analysis was two tailed.

Results

Demographic variables like age, sex, height, weight and ASA physical status and also duration of surgery in both the study groups are comparable ($p > 0.05$), (Table 1)

Table 1: demographic characteristics and duration of surgery

Group →	Ropivacaine (A) N=50		Bupivacaine (B) N=50		P-value
	Variable ↓	Mean	S.D	Mean	
Age (Years)	41.08	±11.81	40.5	±12.99	0.81
Weight(Kg)	59.02	±4.01	59.88	±3.56	0.96
Height(cm)	160.4	±4.62	161	±3.63	0.96
Duration of Surgery(mins)	115	±33.47	113	±29.79	0.75

There was no significant difference among the study groups in respect to the time of onset of sensory block at T₁₀ level and S₃ level, duration of sensory block at T₁₀ level and S₃ level (Table 2 and 3)

Table 2: onset of sensory block at t₁₀ level and s₃ level

Onset of Sensory Block (Mins)	MEAN ± S.D.		“p” Value
	Group-A	Group-B	
T ₁₀	12.78±2.6	13±2.6	0.57
S ₃	15.78±2.8	15.72±2.6	0.91

Table 3: Duration of sensory block at t₁₀ level and s₃ level

Duration of Sensory Block (Mins)	MEAN ± S.D.		“p” Value
	Group-A	Group-B	
T ₁₀	207.3±39.9	207.9±36.9	0.93
S ₃	243.3±37	243.8±39.5	0.94

There is a highly significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between the study groups in respect to the duration of motor block (Table 4). The duration of motor block was longer in the study Group B as compared to Group A.

Table 4: Duration of motor block

Duration of Motor Block (Minutes)	MEAN ± S.D.		“p” Value
	Group-A	Group-B	
B ₁	141.2±21.9	189.4±40.2	<0.05
B ₂	102.6±14.9	142.4±37.6	<0.05

86% in group A of patients attained Bromage 2 motor block and 7% attained Bromage 3 motor block. In group B, 24% of patients attained Bromage 2 motor block and 76% attained Bromage 3 motor block. So the patients in

group B attained greater degree of motor block.(Table 5)

Table 5: Maximum degree of motor block

Max Degree of Motor Block	Group A		Group B	
	No.	%	No.	%
B1	0	0	0	0
B2	43	86	12	24
B3	7	14	38	76

The time taken for two segment regression of sensory block in both the groups is statistically insignificant (p value 0.88). Thus they have similar time period for two segment regression of sensory-block (Table 6)

Table 6: Time taken for the sensory block to regress by 2 segments

Mean Time (minutes)	MEAN \pm S.D.		“p” Value
	Group-A	Group-B	
	156 \pm 35.2	157 \pm 36.4	0.88

After epidural anaesthesia fall in heart rate was seen in both the groups. After statistical analysis, no significant difference was found among the patients of group A and group B at any time in the study period. There was no significant difference between the patients of group A and group B the

groups as far as SpO₂ was concerned at any time in the study period.

The incidence of side effects are similar in both the study groups. So the drugs are comparable with respect to side effects.(Table 7)

Table 7: Comparison of side effects among the groups

Category	Group-A		Group-B	
	No	%	No	%
Hypotension	9	18	10	20
Bradycardia	5	10	4	8
Nausea	3	6	4	8
Vomiting	1	2	1	2
Shivering	5	10	4	8
Urinary Retention	3	6	2	4
Pruritus	3	6	3	6

There was no significant difference among the study groups with respect to the time for onset of post-operative analgesia (Table 8)

Table 8: Onset of post operative analgesia

Onset Of Post Operative Analgesia	MEAN \pm S.D.		“p” Value
	Group-A	Group-B	
Minimum Time (min)	10	12	0.92
Maximum Time (min)	18	18	
Mean \pm S.D.	14.26 \pm 2.27	14.22 \pm 2.25	

There was no significant difference among the study groups in respect to post-operative analgesia. So the study drugs are comparable in respect to duration of post-operative analgesia (Table 9)

Table 9: Duration of post operative analgesia

Duration Of Post Operative Analgesia	MEAN \pm S.D.		“p” Value
	Group-A	Group-B	
Maximum Duration (min)	180	180	0.87
Minimum Duration (min)	300	285	
Mean \pm S.D.	221.4 \pm 30.8	222.3 \pm 26.1	

There was no significant difference (p=0.48) between the patients of study group A and group B in respect to VAS score at the time of request of analgesic by the patients (Table 10)

Table 10: Visual analogue scale score at the time of request of rescue analgesic

VAS score	Group A	Group B	P value
Minimum score	4	4	0.48
Maximum score	6	6	
Mean \pm SD	5.26 \pm 0.69	5.14 \pm 0.7	

The groups are comparable in terms of maximum intra operative VAS score (Table 11)

Table 11: Maximum intraoperative vas score

Maximum Intra operative VAS Score	Group A		Group B	
	No.	%	No.	%
0	47	94	48	96
1	2	4	2	4
2	1	2	0	0
3-10	0	0	0	0

Discussion

Epidural anaesthesia is now being increasingly used for orthopaedic procedures of lower limbs compared to general anaesthesia.[4] Epidural anaesthesia has several advantages over general anaesthesia like decrease in stress responses to surgery, improved post-operative analgesia, decreased incidence of nausea and vomiting and less respiratory and cardiac depression.[5] The development of long-acting amide local anaesthetics has traditionally focused on ever increasing duration of local anaesthetics. Development of ropivacaine diverges from this tradition because its duration of sensory anaesthesia is similar to that of currently available local anaesthetics. [6] Also it is different from other local anaesthetics because it is prepared as a single enantiomer(s), rather than a racemic mixture. Clinical importance of this difference may be related to a separation of local anaesthetic potency and potential for cardiotoxicity. [7] The present study was designed to compare 0.5% bupivacaine hydrochloride and 0.75% ropivacaine hydrochloride for epidural anaesthesia in adult patients undergoing lower extremity surgery. [8] The two groups are comparable in terms of onset of sensory block in our study which coincides with the studies of David L Brown et al(1990), Sara Korula et al(2011) and A P Wolff et al(1995). [9] The time for 2 segment regression is for ropivacaine and bupivacaine is similar, which implies that the duration is similar for both the groups in our study coinciding with the studies of David L Brown et al(1990) A P Wolff et al(1995) and Sara Korula et al(2011). Ropivacaine produces shorter duration of motor block compared to bupivacaine. This is similar to what found by David L Brown et al (1990), A P Wolff et al(1995) and Sara Korula et al(2011). [10-13]There was no significant difference in change of hemodynamic parameters two study groups which corroborates with the findings of David L Brown et al (1990), Sara Korula et al(2011), A P Wolff et al(1995) and Brendan T Finucane et al (1996). The duration of post-operative analgesia for ropivacaine and for bupivacaine is statistically not different. This result corroborates with that found by Sara Korula et al(2011), Negri P D et al(2004) and Casati A et al(2003). The incidence of side effects are similar in both the study groups. So the drugs are comparable with respect to side effects similar to studies of Sara Korula et al(2011), Edward Crosby et al(1998)

Brendan T Funicane(1996) and Edward Crosby et al(1998). [14,15]

Conclusion

Bupivacaine (0.5%) and Ropivacaine (0.75%) produce similar epidural anaesthesia with the only exception that the degree and duration of motor block is less with ropivacaine.

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